

Sentiment-Feedback Analysis For User Reviews Using Machine Learning Algorithm

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Abstract— To pick people's attitudes toward events, organizations and products, companies, people, and more, "sentiments" were gathered from social media updates, online news stories, user reviews, and more. In this work, moods are divided into several chapters. The proposed methodology is based on various machine learning algorithms. The data set used in the analysis taken from Twitter. The goal of this problem is to find nasty remarks in tweets. For the sake of simplicity, if a tweet associated with a racist or sexist attitude, tweet is considered offensive. As a result, it is difficult to identify the difference between racist or sexist tweets and other tweets.

Keywords— F1 score, detection of hate expressions or languages, Tweet.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, all the apps we used are connected to the internet. People use a variety of internet venues to express their thoughts, ideas, and opinions. The technique of recognizing and categorizing feelings in a source text is known as sentiment analysis. Tweets often help generate a large amount of sentiment data during analysis. These statistics are useful in determining public opinion on a variety of topics. Formally, looking at a training sample of tweets and tags, with a "1" label denoting racist/sexist tweets and a "0" designating non-racist/sexist tweets. In this paper, we use a machine learning algorithm to classify user reviews as racist/sexist or non-racist/sexist and generate user F1 scores.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

- [1] Kaur (2015) offers a set of geographical flood data gathered from Twitter that captures individual opinions. They classified the data using the Naive Bayes equation, which yielded findings with a 67 percent accuracy. They will need to collect a large number of individual decisions that will benefit every governmental and non-governmental body in order to deal with such a situation more effectively. These strategies are less complicated than the formula based on a lexicon.
- [2] The final match of the 2015 Indian Premier League was described by Paul in 2017. The purpose of this article is to investigate IPL match standards, as well as the fact that this player is well-known and this squad is dominant. Hadoop and an artificial language reduction map are required. They received a score similar to MS Dhoni's, which has been widely

discussed in relation to the players and the City Indians' strong team. This method yielded a better result.

- [3] The criteria and impact of sentiment analysis for an online platform are described by Mittal in 2016. They must also provide a list of feelings, as well as input and comments derived from articles and regular updates. They need a result to check if the reviews and publications are helpful to the customer, and purchasers like to go to websites on the internet.
- [4] Anto, 2016 describes the analysis of feelings of abuse in merchandise classification. When it comes to product promotion, customer feedback might assist a producer in getting the greatest outcomes. They will make changes to his product in response to the comments they receive. Some users are notorious for failing to communicate their feedback. The purpose of this study is to solve the challenge of delivering feedback by developing technology that can provide automated feedback based on Twitter data. They used SVM technology and got an eighty percent accurate result. This approach provides rapid and helpful feedback.
- [5] Saragih, describes 2017s in relation to customer engagement by analyzing social media feedback in online transmission. TF-IDF technology is used here.

III. MOTIVATION

1. Toxic online content has become a major issue in today's society as a result of the exponential growth in internet usage by people of different ethnicities and educational backgrounds. Distinguishing between hate speech and offensive language in the automatic detection of hazardous text material is a serious challenge. In this study, we suggested a method for automatically categorising tweets on Twitter into two groups: hate speech and non-hate speech. We test multiple machine learning models employing a bag of terms and the term frequency-inverse document frequency (TFIDF) values on the Twitter dataset. In a comparison research, we compare the models employing each of these methodologies.

IV. METHODOLOGY

We've completed all of the necessary pre-modeling processes to get the data into the right shape and format. We'll build models using datasets with a variety of features.

We use the various algorithms to build models:

1. Logistic Regression
2. Support Vector Machine
3. Random Forest
4. XGBoost

1. Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression is most commonly used machine learning algorithms, which comes under the supervised learning technique. It is a technique for predicting dependent variables from a collection of independent variables.

2. Support Vector Machine

SVM is a supervised machine learning technique that can be used to classify and predict data. Despite the fact that we state regression problems are ideal for categorization. The SVM algorithm's purpose is to find a hyperplane in an N-dimensional space that categorizes input points in a unique way.

3. Random Forest

In supervised learning, Random Forest is a well-known machine learning algorithm. It can be used for classification and regression in machine learning. It is based on the concept of group learning, which is the process of combining numerous classifiers to solve a complex problem and improve model performance.

4. XGBoost

Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) is a scalable machine learning toolkit that stands for Gradient Boosted Distributed Decision Tree (GBDT). It is the top machine learning package for regression, classification, and ordering issues, and it supports parallel tree augmentation.

V. BUILD MODEL

- Importing libraries

```
import re # for regular expressions
import pandas as pd
pd.set_option("display.max_colwidth", 200)
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import string
import nltk # for text manipulation
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=DeprecationWarning)

%matplotlib inline
```

- Uploading datasets

```
from google.colab import files
uploaded = files.upload()

Choose Files train_E6oV3lV.csv
• train_E6oV3lV.csv(text/csv) - 3103165 bytes, last modified: 5/31/2022 - 100% done
Saving train_E6oV3lV.csv to train_E6oV3lV.csv

from google.colab import files
uploaded = files.upload()

Choose Files test_tweets_anuFYb8.csv
• test_tweets_anuFYb8.csv(text/csv) - 1635543 bytes, last modified: 5/31/2022 - 100% done
Saving test_tweets_anuFYb8.csv to test_tweets_anuFYb8.csv

● Examine the training and testing datasets.

[ ] train = pd.read_csv('train_E6oV3lV.csv')
    test = pd.read_csv('test_tweets_anuFYb8.csv')
```

Preparing raw data for use in a machine learning model is known as data preparation. Data cleaning is a crucial stage in the data preprocessing process.

- Inspect the dataset and check out non-racist/sexist tweets and racist/sexist tweets.
- Different algorithms use different features to find F1 score.

The features used by various machine learning algorithms are:

1. Bag-of-Words
2. TF-IDF—Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency
3. Word2Vec
4. Doc2Vec

	Bag-of-Words (F1-score)	TF-IDF (F1-score)	Word2Vec (F1-score)	Doc2Vec (F1-score)
Logistic Regression	0.567	0.564	0.661	0.381
Support Vector Machine	0.554	0.546	0.654	0.214
Random forest	0.598	0.589	0.549	0.07
XG Boost	0.554	0.554	0.698	0.374

